

From Where We Create: Gendered and Decolonial Perspectives on Situated Artistic Practices in Mixed Electroacoustic Music

Iracema de Andrade Almeida

Centro Nacional de Investigación, Documentación e Información Musical “Carlos Chávez”
Mexico

cenidim.ideandrade@inba.edu.mx

Abstract

While the historical subordination of women creators and performers has been widely examined and made visible within dominant Western narratives, many of the ideological frameworks that sustain these inequalities continue to persist in the Global South. Within the field of electroacoustic music, patriarchal and Eurocentric values rooted in colonial discourse still shape aesthetic hierarchies, institutional practices, and models of production. This presentation examines the work of the collective *Féminas Sonoras* as a critical response to these dynamics, asking whether audiovisual and electroacoustic media can function as spaces of resistance and re-signification. The conceptual framework and the majority of the ideas and references mobilized here are developed in my article (De Andrade Almeida 2025)¹, which presents the results of the artistic research carried out through the *Féminas Sonoras* collective. Drawing from interdisciplinary feminist practices that recuperate and reconfigure artistic gestures in order to disrupt binary structures and resist essentialist representations, this research extends such strategies into visual, sonic, and performative domains. Through works for electroacoustic media, five-string electric cello, synthesizer, and video, *Féminas Sonoras* interrogates the relationship between gendered embodiment, sound technologies, improvisation, and creative agency. Central to this approach is the assertion that electroacoustic media is not gender-neutral, but historically inscribed within structures of power. By integrating autobiographical narratives, practices of remembrance, and the explicit defiance of the disciplined female body paradigm, the performances foreground how identity, corporeality, and gender generate indissoluble continuities between stage presence and the intrinsic meanings of these works.

1. Situated Practices in Mixed Electroacoustic Music

Gendered power structures in music have not disappeared; rather, they have shifted unevenly across geopolitical contexts. These dynamics are sustained through normative discourses expressed in dominant ideas, aesthetics, theories, and institutional narratives that define what is considered legitimate or valuable within music culture. Scholars such as Marcia Citron, Suzanne Cusick, Lucy Green, and Susan McClary demonstrated long ago how Western art

¹ De Andrade Almeida, Iracema. Creating from the Body: Gendered Agency in Contemporary Music Performance. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1590/SciELOPreprints.13797>.

music traditions have historically and systematically positioned women in subordinate roles—marginalizing them as composers, creators, and musical thinkers; framing them primarily as interpreters, muses, or amateurs; and associating authority, innovation, and authorship with masculinity. Although in many Euro-American academic and artistic contexts these ideas have been publicly challenged through feminist musicology, gender studies, and broader institutional reforms and discursive shifts, this does not imply that underrepresentation has been resolved. Rather, it suggests that openly sexist frameworks have become less acceptable within official discourse. Many of the ideological structures that sustain inequality, however, continue to operate in the Global South. While Western narratives often present themselves as “post-gender” or progressive, colonial, patriarchal, and Eurocentric structures persist more visibly in Global South contexts, frequently reinforced through imported Western canons and institutions, unequal access to resources and recognition, and conservative academic and cultural infrastructures.

This asymmetry often remains obscured: feminist critiques may be institutionally acknowledged, yet the power relations they seek to dismantle continue to operate—often in more rigid and normalized forms—within Global South contexts. An examination of diverse artistic practices reveals that gender inequality in music is not eliminated but unevenly displaced across different professional and geopolitical contexts (Bull 2019; Cumming 2000; Yoshihara 2007; McCormick 2015; McMullen 2006; Nogueira and O’Keefe 2023), a condition that becomes particularly legible when approached through a decolonial lens. In this regard, decolonial thought offers a critical framework for intervening in these dynamics. As Gómez Moreno argues, decolonial aesthetics should not be understood as a style or method, but as a situated and critical practice grounded in lived experience, memory, and the sensibilities of communities shaped by colonial systems of power, affirming plural and context-specific ways of creating and perceiving art (Moreno Gómez 2019; 2021).

Within the domain of electroacoustic music, patriarchal and Eurocentric values rooted in hegemonic colonial discourse continue to shape aesthetic hierarchies, institutional practices, and models of production. The legacy of colonialism compounds gendered hierarchies, sustaining performer–composer binaries and reinforcing Western aesthetic paradigms as universal standards. Although contemporary shifts in some global contexts have begun to challenge the absolute authority of the score, the composer, and the disciplinary control of the performer’s body, such transformations remain uneven. In many conservatories, festivals, and concert spaces outside the Euro-American sphere, fidelity to the canon continues to function as a dominant legitimizing force. Yet, despite these constraints, the question is not only how female performers have been restricted by canonical ideologies, but also how their artistic practices can actively intervene in and reshape these structures, enabling new models of musical creation and practice to emerge as powerful sites of transformation and expansion. In performance contexts informed by feminist, queer, and decolonial aesthetics, female artists reclaim visual and sonic self-definition. By foregrounding their bodies as active sites of expression and meaning—rather than as passive objects of display—these practices disrupt the logic of spectatorship embedded in male-centered artistic traditions. In this sense, female performers who center corporeality do not merely contest dominant aural and visual regimes; they also reconfigure the ethical and interpretive relationship between performer and audience. Musical meaning emerges here as a co-produced process in which body, subjectivity, and identity operate relationally, exceeding the limits imposed by hierarchical models of production and reception. From my standpoint as a Brazilian–Mexican cellist who

identifies as a woman and works primarily within contemporary music performance, I engage these questions by proposing an alternative framework grounded in embodied and situated knowledge. This perspective does not presume a homogeneous or universal experience of womanhood. Rather, the reflections and analyses developed here emerge from a specific positionality: that of a Latin American female performer working with audiovisual and mixed electroacoustic practices. While other intersecting axes—such as race, class, sexuality, ability, and geopolitical location—are recognized as central to any critical account of artistic agency, they fall beyond the scope of the present discussion. These dimensions remain vital areas for future research committed to explicitly intersectional approaches.

2. *Féminas Sonoras* as a Laboratory of Experimentation

Taken together, *Féminas Sonoras* enables modes of artistic research and creation that traditional frameworks of Western concert music tend to marginalize or render invisible. Rather than privileging fixed scores, hierarchical authorship, or the presumed neutrality of sound technologies, the collective foregrounds embodied knowledge, collaborative processes, and situated subjectivities as central agents of musical meaning. While *Féminas Sonoras* was conceived and developed as a collective project based on shared authorship, the analyses and works discussed in this presentation are grounded in my own artistic practice as a performer and sound/music creator. Accordingly, I adopt the pronoun “we” when referring to the collective’s shared conceptual frameworks, collaborative processes, and common research premises, and “I” when addressing my individual artistic decisions, contributions, and situated inquiries. This distinction reflects a methodological commitment to articulating knowledge from embodied practice, while remaining attentive to the collective conditions within which that practice emerged. Drawing from interdisciplinary feminist practices, in which women artists have long explored the recuperation and reconfiguration of artistic gestures to disrupt binary structures and resist essentialist representations, our project extends such strategies into the realm of visual, sonic, and performative arts. We investigate how audiovisual mixed electroacoustic music, as both a material and symbolic practice, could be instrumentalized to question the normative configurations of gender and the female body. Through processes of creation of works for electroacoustic sounds, five-string electric cello, synthesizer, and video, *Féminas Sonoras* interrogated the relationship between gendered embodiment, sound technologies, improvisation and creative agency, foregrounding the notion that electroacoustic media is not gender-neutral, but historically and materially coded within structures of power.

Inspired by cultures of remembrance of the feminine (Seydel 2014; 2018) and the defiance of the disciplined female body paradigm (Bull 2019; Cusick 1994; 1999; Green 1997), the autobiographical narrative and feminine representations, within an expanded framework of audiovisual electroacoustic performance, serve as catalytic elements that project their representational power and the production of meaning in a counter-hegemonic way. Thus, identity, corporeality, and gender generate indissoluble continuities between the stage presence of the female performer and the intrinsic meanings of the work. These creative possibilities are explored as destabilizing agents of the normative force of tradition and the roles historically assigned to women in Western art music. In this context, the works presented and discussed as case studies position themselves as responses to the prevailing artistic norms in academia and electroacoustic music traditions. They underscore the unique

potential of audiovisual mixed electroacoustic music to stimulate critique within intellectual, artistic, and societal discourse, while promoting new artistic ecologies and reexamining the role of female musicians in times of sociopolitical challenges. *Céu da Boca*, *Ronín*, *Espectros de Água*, and *Rabeca*—explore themes of life, death, memory, and identity through embodied female imaginaries shaped by affect and cultural inscription. In doing so, they demonstrate how interdisciplinary creation can advance both artistic and theoretical debates, while situating female subjectivity/identity at the center of electroacoustic and audiovisual performance practice. In this context, I position myself as a *performer-creator*, a category I propose to subvert the historical separation between composition and performance, and to destabilize the Cartesian dualism between mind and body that has sustained the disciplinary model of the performer (Cusick 1994; 1999). This self-identification with the *performer-creator* aligns with the idea of an artist who generates her own sonic and musical materials while also performing them in concert, thus establishing a unified creative process. In my practice, composing involves improvisation, technological mediation, centrality of corporeality and shared authorship—modes of creation often deemed peripheral within canonical frameworks. My refusal to conform to the normative image of the composer is not a rejection of creative authority, but a deliberate repositioning. At the core of this proposal lies what I call the *female sonic body*—an entity that transcends mere physicality to become a gendered, situated, and culturally inscribed corporeality. In my case, my *female sonic body* is inseparable from the instrument I inhabit: the cello. My body and the cello form a deeply interwoven expressive system within this new repertoire, activating a sonic and visual device through which meaning is generated, performed, and perceived. My female sonic body thus functions as a dynamic site in which subjectivity and identity are not only represented but enacted.

*Céu da Boca*² (2021)—a Portuguese title that translates as *Firmament of the Mouth*—refers simultaneously to the anatomical palate and to a symbolic space of emergence. In the sonic realm, the work explores the idea of primordial sound as a creative force. According to the Mayan Popol Vuh, the universe was not constructed through physical labor but brought into being through sound—through the act of speaking. This cosmology situates voice as a generative force capable of materializing worlds. In *Céu da Boca*, this concept is transposed to an intimate scale, focusing on the subtle yet potent sounds that emerge from the mouth beyond articulated language. Breath, resonance, and vocal friction become sites of sonic creation, foregrounding the mouth not merely as a physiological apparatus but as a threshold between interiority and world-making. *Ronín*³ (2021) draws on a different yet complementary symbolic framework. The title refers to the spiritual serpent, guardian of the sacred ayahuasca plant, and the piece engages with Indigenous Amazonian healing chants, particularly those associated with Shipibo-Konibo female healers. These vocal traditions are evoked through my own singing in the final section of the work, not as an act of imitation but as a situated resonance. Through this gesture, *Ronín* foregrounds voice as a conduit of embodied knowledge, ritual memory, and feminine spiritual lineage, situating the performer's vocal

² *Céu da Boca* (2021), for electroacoustic sounds, 5-string eCello, synthesizer, and video. Iracema de Andrade, musical and electroacoustic creation, 5-string electric cello, voice, and audio design. Jessica Rodríguez, visual composition, photography, editing, and image post-production. <https://youtu.be/VFemGoYkKmk>

³ *Ronín* (2021), for electroacoustic sounds, 5-string eCello, synthesizer, and video. Iracema de Andrade, musical and electroacoustic creation, 5-string electric cello, voice, and audio design. Jessica Rodríguez, visual composition, photography, editing, and image post-production. <https://youtu.be/vvyhCMBVddg>

presence within a broader cosmological and epistemic field. Across both works, spectromorphological design plays a central role. The sonic materials unfold along a continuum that moves from source-bonded sounds—most notably the voice—toward increasingly abstract and spectral morphologies. Even as these sounds become decontextualized, they retain a strong affective charge. Drawing on Cusick’s understanding of voice as a projection of the body’s interior outward, my virtual voice in these works can be understood as a site where gendered identity is enacted: “the voice is the body, its very breath and interior shapes projected outward into the world as a way others might know us” (Cusick 1999, 29). In this sense, vocal sound functions not merely as acoustic material but as an extension of corporeality and subjectivity.

The layered visual and sonic narratives become embedded within the performance itself, generating a sensorial dissonance that unsettles fixed boundaries between physical presence and virtual projection. Close framings of specific parts of my body and of my cello transform mimetic and figurative elements into magnified, mobile fragments. These images dialogue with the ghostly presence of my voice in the electroacoustic space and with my instrumental gestures onstage. This dual presence—simultaneously live and mediated—produces a form of expanded corporeality in which body and instrument become inseparably linked. Together, they form a unified yet amplified entity, the *female sonic body*. These creations are inseparably tied to my subjectivity and identity as a *performer-creator*. Their significance derives not only from my body as a biological entity, but also from the symbolic, cultural, and historical inscriptions it carries. Performance thus becomes a site where embodied experience, memory, and authorship converge, challenging reductive separations between interpretation and creation.

This framework is further developed in *Espectros de Água* (2021) and *Rabeca* (2021), which focus explicitly on affective memory and the production of identity. Our shared aim was to explore feminine archetypes rooted in my genealogical history and affective memory. The audiovisual language of these pieces draws extensively on personal archives, particularly family photographs, in which the material presence of my foremothers is recontextualized in dialogue with my own gendered identity in the twenty-first century. On stage, my *female sonic body* becomes linked to these ancestral presences—spectral yet embodied—transforming each work into a symbolic space of remembrance. In *Espectros de Água*⁴, images of my female ancestors merge with my own presence, interwoven with sonic metaphors of water, blood, veins, and rivers. These elements connect generations through an imagined umbilical cord, articulating continuity and rupture simultaneously. In *Rabeca*⁵, the sonic material draws from the traditional fiddle of Brazil’s Northeast. Its characteristic *resfulengo* bowing—producing syncopated rhythms associated with *baião*—is transposed onto the electric cello and combined with field recordings of church bells. Through spectral transformation, tone gradually dissolves into noise, destabilizing inherited musical forms while preserving their affective resonance.

⁴ *Espectros de Água* (2021), for electroacoustic sounds, 5-string eCello, synthesizer, and video. Iracema de Andrade, electroacoustic and musical creation, 5-string electric cello, and audio design. Adela Marín, visual creation, photography, editing, and image post-production. <https://youtu.be/UBPafh5IVd0>

⁵ *Rabeca* (2021), for electroacoustic sounds, 5-string eCello, synthesizer, and video. Iracema de Andrade, electroacoustic and musical creation, 5-string electric cello, and audio design. Adela Marín, visual creation, photography, editing, and imagepost-production. <https://youtu.be/mkj-lhVHWMQ>

Drawing on Pierre Nora's concept of *lieux de mémoire* (1989), these works function as spaces through which I attempt to reassemble a disrupted sense of belonging. They are informed by Marianne Hirsch's notion of *postmemory* (1992-93; 1999), in which memories of previous generations are transmitted not through direct experience but through mediated narratives, images, and affective traces. By engaging with these materials, I construct a personal narrative that operates simultaneously as an act of self-representation and self-reconstitution. Within this framework, the *female sonic body* emerges as the performative site through which layers of cultural, genealogical, and affective memory unfold. This *performer-creator* position is further articulated through an approach that disrupts the authority of the written score and reclaims the body as a compositional agent. In this repertoire, the cello part is improvisatory. During performance, I follow the video projection on a side monitor, where each visual cue—movement, color, texture—functions as a real-time compositional prompt. Improvisation here is not randomness, but a situated response: an embodied dialogue with sound and image. This mode of real-time creation is adaptive and dialogic, yet also deeply intuitive and personal, aligning with what may be described as situated improvisation. By displacing the centrality of the score, this approach blurs the boundaries between composition and performance, resisting Western notions of musical autonomy while affirming ephemerality and variability as legitimate forms of authorship. As sound and image fuse in performance, the *female sonic body* enacts what Nicholas Cook (2023) describes as the “musicalisation of the body,” in which the body itself becomes a musical parameter—an active site of meaning rather than a neutral medium of transmission. Through this process, performance becomes a critical practice through which identity, memory, and agency are continuously negotiated and reimaged (Laws et al. 2019).

3. Final Thoughts on Reclaiming the *Female Sonic Body* as a Site of Agency

To perform mixed electroacoustic music as a woman within Western concert traditions is to inhabit a historically disciplined body shaped by aesthetic norms that privilege autonomy, abstraction, and neutrality, while obscuring the gendered conditions under which musical meaning is produced. As Green (1997) has observed, although classical music discourse is often framed around ideals of universality, the gender of the music professional plays a decisive—yet frequently unacknowledged—role in shaping how music is made, perceived, and valued. Within this context, foregrounding corporeality rather than concealing it becomes a critical gesture. In the repertoire discussed here, the deliberate exposure of the body functions as a means of rendering visible the ideologies that have historically regulated it. By intervening in the circular relationship between identity, perception, and meaning, these works transform embodiment into a site of agency, revealing the body not as something hidden behind the music, but as an active participant in meaning-making. Femininity, in this framework, is not treated as an external or expressive attribute added to music, but as a compositional parameter that actively shapes sonic, visual, and performative structures. As McClary (1991) has argued, women can foreground gendered and sexual subjectivity in music without resorting to essentialism, thereby generating alternative musical languages that resist dominant paradigms. Yet, despite these theoretical advances, there remains a striking lack of documentation and visibility of Latin American women working within electroacoustic music from such embodied and critical positions. By drawing on popular, mestiza, and feminist imaginaries, the *female sonic body* operating in these works intervenes

critically in the hierarchies of race, gender, and value that continue to structure Western art music. These aesthetics reclaim expressive forms that have been historically devalued or rendered invisible, rearticulating them through voice, gesture, technology, and image. To create from the body, in this sense, is to reclaim authorship and to articulate alternative epistemologies of sound grounded in lived, situated experience rather than ideologies of musical autonomy. The *performer-creator* paradigm proposed through this practice does not simply offer a new methodological approach; it advances a different ontology of music-making. In this model, composition and performance are inseparable, knowledge emerges through embodiment, and presence itself becomes a subversive act. Performance unsettles inherited hierarchies, challenges the presumed neutrality of the performer's body, and reclaims artistic agency as a form of resistance.

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